

Project No: 862681
Project acronym: ROSEWOOD4.0

Project title:

EU Network of Regions On Sustainable WOOD mobilisation ready for digitalisation

Programme: H2020-RUR-2018-2020 (Rural Renaissance)

Topic: RUR-15-2018-2019-2020 Thematic networks compiling knowledge ready for practice

Start date of project: 01.01.2020

Duration: 30 months

Deliverable D1.4

Digital innovations and best practices in sustainable wood mobilisation – Videos (target of 25 video clips completed and delivered to EIP-AGRI)

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Due date of deliverable: 31.12.2021

Actual submission date: 31.01.2022

Work Package	WP1 – Assessing / Enabling the potential of best practices in EU-regions
Associated Task	Task 1.2 Selection of relevant best practices and preparation of dissemination materials
Covered Period	M1-M24
Deliverable Lead Partner	EFI
Version	1.2

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

CHANGE CONTROL

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Change History	Author(s)	Organisation
1.0	23.12.2021	Initial version	Eduard Mauri	EFI
1.1	23.12.2021	Review	Javier Casado	SIG
1.2	31.01.2022	Final version	Eduard Mauri	EFI

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Abstract

By end of January 2022, 26 short videos describing a best practice or innovation were published. Eleven of the 13 domains, and 12 of the 25 types of solutions tackled in ROSEWOOD4.0 were represented. All the seven challenges addresses are covered. The five hubs have produced between four and seven videos each, mostly with a duration between 3 and 7 minutes. All the videos except one have an associated factsheet in the *Knowledge platform for regional forest innovation*, where they are also featured.

Deviations

The target of 25 videos describing a best practice or innovation by end of 2021 could not be achieved. Twenty-four short videos were published by 31 December 2021. As two more videos were almost ready by that time, the submission of this deliverable was postponed to January 2022 to feature the whole collection of 26 videos.

1. Methodology

EFI, as leader of the WP4 *Communication, dissemination, exploitation and collaboration with other initiatives to maximise impact*, provided the guidelines to produce the videos to all partners, which were the responsible to produce the videos for the selected best practices and innovations from their own countries. Main guidelines concerned:

- The correct usage of the ROSEWOOD4.0 logo,
- The correct usage of the EU-funding and H2020 disclaimer,
- Guidelines and templates for the intro and the outro,
- The expected length of the video,
- The quality and format requirements for sound and video recording,
- The structure of the video.

Once the videos were produced, they were sent to EFI, who reviewed, requested modifications (if needed) and published them (see section 3. *Dissemination efforts*).

2. Results

2.1 Summary of published videos

Table 1. Number of videos per hub of origin.

Hub	Count
Central-East Hub	4
Central-West Hub	4
North Hub	7
South-East Hub	6
South-West Hub	5
Total	26

Figure 1. Number of videos by duration.

Table 2. Number of domains of the best practices and innovations presented in the videos.

Domains ^a	Count
Education and training	4
Forest disturbances, risks	3
Forest management, ecosystem, resilience	8
Forest-based bio/circular economy	2
Harvesting, infrastructure, logistics	7
Innovation management, hubs, clusters	2
Inventory, monitoring	9
Ownership, cooperation	4
Products, markets, trade	3
Research and development	2
Wood construction industry	1
Total	45

^a One best practice or innovation in a video may be related to more than one domain.

Table 3. Number of types of solution of the best practices and innovations presented in the videos.

Type of solution ^a	Count
Advice and services for forest owners	3
Circular, bio-based products	1
Collaboration platforms, logistical hubs	1
Data platforms, data hubs	4
Design software	1
eLearning, blended learning	3
Joint management	1
Modelling, simulation, optimization	7
Networks, testbeds, R&D platforms	1
Sensors, measurement equipment	1
Smart machinery, equipment	2
Traceability tools	2
Total	27

^a Each best practice or innovation is related to only one type of solution, but one video featured one best practice and one innovation, each one with a different type of solution.

Table 4. Number of challenges of the best practices and innovations presented in the videos.

Challenge addressed ^a	Count
1.- Improve forest resilience and adaption to climate change	5
2.- Improve infrastructures and capacity of public actors	6
3.- Activate private owners and cooperative forest management	3
4.- Ensure a well-trained workforce through attractive skills development and education	4
5.- Enhance economic and environmental performance of forest supply chains	7
6.- Grow the forest-based bioeconomy through circular use and value-added products	1
7.- Raise public awareness, social acceptance and political support for forestry	1
Total	27

^a Each best practice or innovation is related to only one challenge, but one video featured one best practice and one innovation, each one with a different challenge addressed.

Table 5. Number best practices and innovations presented in the videos that are digital solutions.

Are digital solutions?	Count
No	3
Yes	24

Table 6. Number best practices and innovations presented in the videos that are innovative solutions.

Are innovative solutions?	Count
No	6
Yes	21

2.2 List of published videos

Title	Virtual Forest 2.0
Summary	ROSEWOOD4.0 features in this video Finland's "Virtual Forest 2.0", which is a new innovation tool that enables efficient visualization of forest resource and spatial data in 3D. It can be used for example in participatory planning of land use and as a guidance of forest owners.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-virtual-forest-finland/
Duration	3'00" minutes
Date of publication	9 June 2021
Domains	Inventory, monitoring Ownership, cooperation
Type of solution	Modelling, simulation, optimization
Challenge addressed	3.- Activate private owners and cooperative forest management
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Finland (North Hub)

Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/virtual-forest-20
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Title	Wood terminals
Summary	ROSEWOOD4.0 features in this video Finland's "Wood Terminals" as a best practice from the country's timber-producing provinces, such as Lapland.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-wood-terminals-finland/
Duration	9'55" minutes
Date of publication	16 April 2021
Domains	Harvesting, infrastructure, logistics
Type of solution	Collaboration platforms, logistical hubs
Challenge addressed	5.- Enhance economic and environmental performance of forest supply chains
Digital solution	No
Innovation	No
County and hub	Finland (North Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/joint-wood-terminals

Title	Arboair
Summary	In this ROSEWOOD4.0 video we present a technological innovation for forest managers suffering from the effects of climate change on their forests. Arboair is a Swedish company that uses drones, colour change analysis and artificial intelligence to scan the forest for infected or stressed trees. By identifying the damage in time, Arboair technology can prevent the bark beetle from spreading further in the forest. In addition, thanks to this technology, the forest inventory count is ten times faster than with traditional methods on foot.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-arboair-sweden/
Duration	3'52" minutes
Date of publication	5 October 2021
Domains	Inventory, monitoring Forest disturbances, risks Research and development
Type of solution	Sensors, measurement equipment
Challenge addressed	1.- Improve forest resilience and adaption to climate change
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Sweden (North Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/arboair-high-precision-imagery-bark-beetle-detection

Title	Virtual reality in the forest
Summary	ROSEWOOD4.0 presents in this video a new example of innovation and digitalisation in the Swedish forestry industry. Through the company HIAB and its digital solution HiVision, the Swedish forestry sector is currently helping to increase efficiency, safety, sustainability and equality to enhance and modernise forest-related businesses.

Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/virtual-reality-forest-sweden/
Duration	4'08" minutes
Date of publication	2 September 2021
Domains	Products, markets, trade Harvesting, infrastructure, logistics Education and training
Type of solution	Smart machinery, equipment
Challenge addressed	5.- Enhance economic and environmental performance of forest supply chains
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Sweden (North Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/hivision-virtual-reality-support-crane-operators

Title	Solør Videregående Skole
Summary	Established 75 years ago, Solør Videregående Skole has since been a national leader in Norway in training for forestry operations. Teaching takes place both indoors and outdoors and allows pupils a practical approach to forestry. The curriculum follows the yearly season with planning, forest culture and logging. Drones are used as a supplement to teaching, where they film objects and stock as a basis for work in teaching. When training operation of forestry machines, drones allow students and teachers to see the work from a birds-eye perspective. Used correctly, this may lead to increased learning both for those who observe, but especially for those who are observed and who get to see themselves at work.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-solor-norway/
Duration	4'10" minutes
Date of publication	1 December 2021
Domains	Harvesting, infrastructure, logistics Education and training
Type of solution	eLearning, blended learning
Challenge addressed	4.- Ensure a well-trained workforce through attractive skills development and education
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Norway (North Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/use-drones-educating-forestry-operators-0

Title	FeltGIS AS
Summary	FeltGIS offers technical solutions for logistics of forest data. This digital solution provides an overview of production and storage with real-time data with a green router - regardless of the color and brand of the machine. The solution from FeltGIS AS provides better information flow from harvesters in the operational logistics from forest to industry.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-feltgis-norway/
Duration	4'37" minutes

Date of publication	23 November 2021
Domains	Forest management, ecosystem, resilience
Type of solution	Smart machinery, equipment
Challenge addressed	5.- Enhance economic and environmental performance of forest supply chains
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Norway (North Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/feltgis

Title	Skogkurs: Forestry Extension Institute
Summary	Skogkurs aims to be the common body for competition in business development and management of forests and other land resources in Norway. Through its activities, Skogkurs contributes to increasing competition among actors in the forest industry, and to disseminating knowledge about forests and nature to schools and the public. Skogkurs has 36 member organisations in Norway. "Active forestry" is a national offer with courses aimed at forest owners, forest workers and forest operators.
Publication link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dZRGgtjO3o&ab_channel=ROSEWOOD4.0Network
Duration	2'49" minutes
Date of publication	22 December 2021
Domains	Forest management, ecosystem, resilience Harvesting, infrastructure, logistics Education and training
Type of solution	eLearning, blended learning
Challenge addressed	4.- Ensure a well-trained workforce through attractive skills development and education
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	No
County and hub	Norway (North Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/skogkurs-forestry-extension-institute

Title	Wald und Holz 4.0 Competence Center
Summary	How can digital means make work around forests and wood faster and more efficient in the future? This is what the Forest and Wood 4.0 Competence Center (KWH4.0) is all about. In order to "smartify" the forest and wood cluster, existing competences from industry, science and administration have to be brought together: the aim of KWH4.0 is to create a knowledge base and infrastructure and to implement forest and wood 4.0 components through innovative Smart Forest Labs, which serve as experimental forestry laboratories in which the developed components, systems and innovations are tested.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-forest-and-wood-4-0-competence-center-germany/
Duration	7'07" minutes

Date of publication	20 October 2021
Domains	Innovation management, hubs, clusters
Type of solution	Modelling, simulation, optimization
Challenge addressed	5.- Enhance economic and environmental performance of forest supply chains
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Germany (Central-West Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/kwh40-center-excellence-forestry-40

Title	FORSITE
Summary	The FORSITE project (Forest site classification Styria-ecological characterization for a dynamic forest site classification) aims to address one of the current forest challenges: improving the resilience of forests and their adaptation to climate change. FORSITE provides forest owners with a great scientific basis such as data on the water storage capacity of the soil, forest site and vegetation mapping in order to make decisions for future tree species selection as well as ensuring climate-fit forest management.
Publication link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cGCGRWZzeO0&ab_channel=ROSEWOOD4.0Network
Duration	4'39" minutes
Date of publication	3 November 2021
Domains	Forest management, ecosystem, resilience
Type of solution	Modelling, simulation, optimization
Challenge addressed	1.- Improve forest resilience and adaption to climate change
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Austria (Central-West Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/forsite-forest-site-classification-styria-ecological-characterization-dynamic-forest-site

Title	ClimaFor
Summary	ROSEWOOD4.0 presents in this video "CLIMAFOR", a best practice and innovation from France. As carbon sequestration has become a priority to tackle climate change, the Centre National de la Propriété Forestière (CNPF) has developed a software and digital tool that aims to make it easier for forest owners to assess the carbon balance of their forest stand and meet the needs for carbon measurements. CLIMAFOR is a decision support tool for forest carbon that aims to optimise the efficiency of carbon sequestration on privately owned forest lands.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-climafor-france/
Duration	4'36" minutes
Date of publication	19 July 2021
Domains	Inventory, monitoring Research and development
Type of solution	Modelling, simulation, optimization

Challenge addressed	1.- Improve forest resilience and adaption to climate change
Digital solution	No
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	France (Central-West Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/climafor-carbon-accounting-tool

Title	La Forêt Bouge
Summary	"La Forêt Bouge" is a digital platform developed in France by the Centre National de la Propriété Forestière (CNPF) for forest owners to help them manage and develop their forest assets. The free services offered include locating plots of land, finding qualified forest management professionals, finding out the price of timber, buying and selling plots (land exchange), among many other benefits. La Forêt Bouge's goal is to encourage contact and to create links between actors in private, economic and institutional domains of the forestry world.
Publication link	https://youtu.be/hGv7jcOEq6c
Duration	5'30" minutes
Date of publication	19 July 2021
Domains	Ownership, cooperation
Type of solution	Advice and services for forest owners
Challenge addressed	3.- Activate private owners and cooperative forest management
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	France (South-West Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/la-foret-bouge-forest-moving

Title	Forest Area Aggregation
Summary	ROSEWOOD4.0 presents in this video an initiative coming from Portugal and promoted by the Baixo Vouga Forestry Association that aims to facilitate the forest management of small forest properties that tend to be abandoned by their owners and pose a risk for the spread of catastrophic forest fires. The innovative Forest Area Aggregation model offers small forest estate owners a way to achieve large-scale efficiencies in forestry operations, improve forest productivity, obtain technical assistance and protect areas of natural interest that are increasingly at risk due to climate change.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/forest-area-aggregation-portugal/
Duration	4'59" minutes
Date of publication	3 September 2021
Domains	Ownership, cooperation Forest management, ecosystem, resilience
Type of solution	Joint management
Challenge addressed	2.- Improve infrastructures and capacity of public actors
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Portugal (South-West Hub)

Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/forest-area-aggregation
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Title	Forest LidaRioja
Summary	<p>The Forest-LidaRioja initiative was created with the aim of developing a forest inventory map and fuel model of the La Rioja region, in northern Spain, using remote sensing technologies. The main practical benefits of this initiative are the importance of improving sustainable forest management and enabling better decision-making and action planning in La Rioja's forest areas.</p> <p>The main results of the Forest-LidaRioja project are the elaboration of a forest inventory of the forests of La Rioja, the mapping of fuel models of the forest area of La Rioja to plan forest fire prevention works, the study of the evolution of poplar groves in the region and their supply potential, as well as technical training on the products generated for professionals interested in their practical use.</p>
Publication link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HhXnSSlbzig&ab_channel=ROSEWOOD4.0Network
Duration	4'30" minutes
Date of publication	17 December 2021
Domains	Inventory, monitoring Harvesting, infrastructure, logistics
Type of solution	Modelling, simulation, optimization
Challenge addressed	2.- Improve infrastructures and capacity of public actors
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Spain (South-West Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/forest-lidarioja-forest-inventory-and-fuel-model-map-using-remote-sensing-technologies-0

Title	LegnOK
Summary	<p>The European Union prohibits the placing on the EU market of timber and timber products of illegal origin (EU Timber Regulation – EUTR). The obligation to adopt measures and procedures aimed at rendering negligible the risk that timber placed on the EU market is of illegal origin falls on "operators", i.e. those who place timber or timber products on the European Community market for the first time.</p> <p>An Italian company, Conlegno, immediately took up the challenge to fight deforestation and promote the market for legally sourced timber. They developed LegnOk: a portal aimed at providing registered operators with useful information on timber and wood derivatives exporting countries (applicable legislation, critical issues, documentation required for due diligence, etc.), together with a logical and guided pathway that allows risk analysis to be carried out.</p>
Publication link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jNJ2P77FLFY&ab_channel=ROSEWOOD4.0Network
Duration	6'41" minutes
Date of publication	1 December 2021

Domains	Inventory, monitoring Products, markets, trade Innovation management, hubs, clusters
Type of solution	Traceability tools
Challenge addressed	5.- Enhance economic and environmental performance of forest supply chains
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Italy (South-West Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/legnok

Title	Forest Data Bank
Summary	The main objective of Poland's Forest Data Bank (Banku Danych o Lasach - BDL) is to provide information on forest management, the state of forests and their changes, irrespective of the form of ownership. Potential users of the resources of the BDL include various levels of management in forestry, environmental protection, education and society. The Forest Data Bank provides information for public statistics, both national and international, as well as for spatial planning.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-forest-data-bank/
Duration	7'48" minutes
Date of publication	19 October 2021
Domains	Inventory, monitoring
Type of solution	Data platforms, data hubs
Challenge addressed	2.- Improve infrastructures and capacity of public actors
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	No
County and hub	Poland (Central-East Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/forest-data-bank

Title	TimFlow
Summary	Timflow is the wood traceability monitoring system implemented by HS Timber Group, which has been largely implemented in Romania. The system allows for the accurate monitoring of the transport route, via GPS, from the place of loading to arrival and excludes shipments of timber from national parks and other sensitive forest habitats. The tool is the perfect solution if you want to know exactly where your timber comes from.
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-timflow-romania/
Duration	3'20" minutes
Date of publication	5 October 2021
Domains	Harvesting, infrastructure, logistics
Type of solution	Traceability tools
Challenge addressed	5.- Enhance economic and environmental performance of forest supply chains
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Romania (Central-East Hub)

Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/timflow-wood-tracking
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Title	LignoSilva
Summary	<p>LignoSilva is a Centre of Excellence of the National Forest Centre in Slovakia that works in cooperation with the Pulp and Paper Institute with a focus on research and innovation in the field of production, mechanical and chemical processing and use wood utilization.</p> <p>Through the implementation of a unique infrastructure (3D CT scanner), LignoSilva focuses on innovation development with companies in the field of wood production, processing and utilisation and contributes to enhance their development and innovation activities related to multipurpose forest management.</p>
Publication link	https://youtu.be/5ug_JW8yltk
Duration	7'41" minutes
Date of publication	15 December 2021
Domains	Forest-based bio/circular economy
Type of solution	Networks, testbeds, R&D platforms
Challenge addressed	2.- Improve infrastructures and capacity of public actors
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Slovakia (Central-East Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/lignosilva-infra-3d-ct-scanner-wood-defect-detection

Title	Electronic Timber Tracking
Summary	<p>From Ukraine we feature an innovation and best practice for timber supply chains: electronic timber tracking. Permanent forest users are obliged to electronically tag each log (or, in the case of firewood, each batch), which makes it possible to establish the legality of its harvesting, namely: description of the log, place and time, name of the purchasing team, transport document. Thanks to this innovation, the system digitally represents the supply chain from the forest to the buyer at the first processing facility.</p>
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-electronic-timber-tracking/
Duration	3'50" minutes
Date of publication	23 November 2021
Domains	Inventory, monitoring
Type of solution	Data platforms, data hubs
Challenge addressed	2.- Improve infrastructures and capacity of public actors
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Ukraine (Central-East Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/electronic-timber-tracking

Title	MojGozdar / MyForester
Summary	ROSEWOOD4.0 project highlights an innovation from Slovenia in this video, aiming to enhance digital tools in the forestry sector. Moj Gozdar (My Forester) is a digital solution that aims to increase the competitiveness of the Slovenian forestry sector by developing and implementing a transparent quality assessment system for forestry contractors. Following the example of online platforms established to connect service providers and subscribers in the economy and tourism and taking into account the specificities of business processes in forestry, Moj Gozdar offers a transparent and objective online information system platform for assessing the suitability of contractors performing one or more forestry services in Slovenia.
Publication link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mmcmYtI5JbQ&ab_channel=ROSEWOOD4.0Network
Duration	4'53" minutes
Date of publication	5 September 2021
Domains	Forest management, ecosystem, resilience Harvesting, infrastructure, logistics Forest-based bio/circular economy
Type of solution	Advice and services for forest owners
Challenge addressed	4.- Ensure a well-trained workforce through attractive skills development and education
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Slovenia (South-East Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/mojgozdar-myforester

Title	Forest National Inventory System
Summary	This ROSEWOOD4.0 video details the modernisation of Slovenia's national inventory system, which has been digitised at every step through data-processing technologies, LIDAR innovation, aerial images and continuous digital monitoring of the country's forest area. All this, thanks to innovation driven by the Slovenian Forestry Institute and the country's Forest National Service.
Publication link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gqp_4W7ZLhM&ab_channel=ROSEWOOD4.0Network
Duration	7'39" minutes
Date of publication	5 October 2021
Domains	Forest management, ecosystem, resilience Forest disturbances, risks
Type of solution	Design software
Challenge addressed	7.- Raise public awareness, social acceptance and political support for forestry
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	No
County and hub	Slovenia (South-East Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/national-forestry-inventory

Title	M Sora
Summary	<p>ROSEWOOD4.0 network had the opportunity to get to know in more detail the Slovenian company M SORA, which is known for its innovation in the woodworking sector.</p> <p>M SORA is a Slovenian woodworking company specialising in the production and installation of doors and windows. A wide range of windows, including lift-and-slide windows and doors, is exported to European countries, USA, Canada, New Zealand, Dubai, and other countries. All wood-based products are custom-made, reflecting the company's constant development, great flexibility and intensive development work on various national and European projects.</p>
Publication link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T2e2YxNE1PI&ab_channel=ROSEWOOD4.0Network
Duration	5'20" minutes
Date of publication	27 July 2021
Domains	Wood construction industry
Type of solution	Circular, bio-based products
Challenge addressed	6.- Grow the forest-based bioeconomy through circular use and value-added products
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Slovenia (South-East Hub)
Factsheet	Not available. Corporate website: https://www.m-sora.si/en/

Title	Sustainable forest management training
Summary	<p>The Institute for Development and International Relations and the Croatian Forests Research Institute in collaboration with other Croatian organisations have established an innovative cooperation to develop and promote educational programmes for adults in the field of sustainable forest management. Through different Erasmus + projects such as VET4BioECONOMY or the CIA2SFM program, Croatian institutions with the collaboration of partners in Slovenia and Austria develop new methods and innovative training techniques that place the forest bioeconomy at the center of the European green agenda.</p> <p>For ROSEWOOD4.0 network, today's and future forestry education and its digitisation is very important as a way to modernise the forest and wood sector. Therefore, from our South East Hub we have selected this example of collaboration and innovation at European level.</p>
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/sustainable-forest-management-training-croatia/
Duration	6'50" minutes
Date of publication	5 August 2021
Domains	Education and training
Type of solution	eLearning, blended learning
Challenge addressed	4.- Ensure a well-trained workforce through attractive skills development and education
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	No

County and hub	Croatia (South-East Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/cooperation-innovative-approach-sustainable-forest-management-training

Title	Public data of forests
Summary	<p>ROSEWOOD4.0 features in this video Croatia's "Public data of forests", which is a digital solution and best practice applied in the country for managing public forests.</p> <p>Croatian Forests Ltd is a company that manages public forests and forest land in Croatia. The company has developed an application containing an overview of public data on the forests it manages. The application in cartographic form presents information in text and table form, as well as spatial illustration of the type of tree species in a specific forest or area. This digital application displays two parameters for each tree species: the total wood volume and the annual growth.</p>
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-innovation-public-data-of-forests-croatia/
Duration	9'02" minutes
Date of publication	18 June 2021
Domains	Forest management, ecosystem, resilience
Type of solution	Data platforms, data hubs
Challenge addressed	2.- Improve infrastructures and capacity of public actors
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Croatia (South-East Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/public-data-forests

Title	SecureChain / SMEs securing future-proof bioenergy chains
Summary	<p>SecureChain is a EU-funded initiative that promotes sustainable bioenergy chains in the rural area, which fulfil high environmental standards and are economically viable for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).</p> <p>From Greece we show you how this initiative has taken shape through companies dedicated to biomass such as AlfaWood, located in the village of Grevena in Western Macedonia province.</p>
Publication link	https://rosewood-network.eu/best-practice-securechain-greece/
Duration	4'57" minutes
Date of publication	16 September 2021
Domains	Products, markets, trade
Type of solution	Modelling, simulation, optimization
Challenge addressed	5.- Enhance economic and environmental performance of forest supply chains
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Greece (South-East Hub)

Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/securechain-small-and-medium-enterprises-securing-future-proof-bioenergy-chains
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Title	Forest challenges and solutions in Central West Europe
Summary	<p>Joint video produced by the ROSEWOOD4.0 Central West Europe Hub analysing the impacts of climate change on forests in Austria, Germany, Switzerland and France and the role of active and sustainable forest management in addressing these challenges.</p> <p>The video features forestry experts from different countries in Central West Europe, who provide a diagnosis of the current situation, as well as solutions and examples of best practices to address climate change issues in the European forestry sector.</p> <p>One innovation and one best practice are presented.</p>
Publication link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gsHKjn3VXfw
Duration	7'05" minutes
Date of publication	28 January 2022
Domains	Inventory, monitoring Owership, cooperation
Type of solution	Data platforms, data hubs Advice and services for forest owners
Challenge addressed	1.- Improve forest resilience and adaption to climate change 3.- Activate private owners and cooperative forest management
Digital solution	Yes No
Innovation	Yes No
County and hub	Austria, Germany, Switzerland and France (Central-West Hub)
Factsheet	Innovation: https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/waldinforw-forest-information-system-nrw-germany Best practice: N/A

Title	SISREP
Summary	<p>SISREP is a project promoted in the region of Castilla y León (Spain) that has developed an advanced statistical model that allows predictive and descriptive analyses to be carried out by means of a tool for predicting the survival of forestations to ensure the success of new plantations. SISREP is based on the use of knowledge from historical site visits to predict the probability of success of future plantations using machine learning techniques, and on a database with more than 50,000 observations referring to forestations carried out from 1993 to the present day.</p>
Publication link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gK9pzd3531c
Duration	6'28" minutes
Date of publication	31 January 2022

Domains	Inventory, monitoring Forest management, ecosystem, resilience Forest disturbances, risks
Type of solution	Modelling, simulation, optimization
Challenge addressed	1.- Improve forest resilience and adaption to climate change
Digital solution	Yes
Innovation	Yes
County and hub	Spain (South-West Hub)
Factsheet	https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en/content/sisrep-management-and-analysis-reforestations-agricultural-land

3. Dissemination efforts

Videos have been disseminated through different communication channels:

- Website of ROSEWOOD4.0 and newsletter: https://rosewood-network.eu/news_media/videos/
- ROSEWOOD4.0 LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/rosewood-network-2b9682165/>
- ROSEWOOD4.0 Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/networkrosewood>
- *Knowledge platform for regional forest innovation* (within the factsheet of each best practice or innovation presented in each video): <https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en>
- Partners' own communication channels

At the time of publishing this deliverable, it is possible that not all videos have been promoted through these channels in order to ensure a continuous flow of varied publications during the months of the project extension. The videos whose "Publishing link" is a youtube.com URL have not yet been disseminated through the ROSEWOOD4.0 communication channels. This will be done in the near future following an editorial calendar of web and social media publications established by WP4.

The videos will also be disseminated through EIP-Agri "Projects" webpage (<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects>). All the videos (except one) present one best practice or one innovation that has a factsheet in the *Knowledge platform for regional forest innovation* (<https://www.forestinnovationhubs.rosewood-network.eu/en>). All these factsheets, once the collection will be completed, will be converted into an EIP-Agri common format factsheets. For those factsheets that have a video related, the URL of the video will be included in the EIP-Agri common format, so the readers will also have access to the videos. In this case, the videos will continue to be stored by a third-party server (YouTube), and not in EIP-Agri's servers. Moreover, this deliverable, once ready, will be sent to a Communications Manager of the EIP-Agri Support Facility to facilitate the dissemination of the videos by EIP-Agri through other means than the EIP-Agri common format factsheets.